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Understanding Digital Alienation in the Digital Natives: A Descriptive Analysis Of Social Networking Sites Usage By Women In Layyah

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study examines digital alienation among women in Layyah, Pakistan, focusing on the ways social networking sites (SNS) are used by three subgroups: educated housewives, college students, and professional workers. Utilizing in-depth interviews (n = 15), thematic analysis was used to study the ways in which technological literacy, privacy issues, socio-cultural norms, and gratifications perceived influence experiences of digital inclusion and alienation. The findings indicate that despite heavy usage of SNS for entertainment and social bonding, structural and cultural barriers restricted digital competencies, privacy fears, and norm policing create senses of exclusion and limited online self-presentation. The research develops uses and gratifications theory by illustrating how gratifications are mediated by social environments and digital capital, and suggests policy and practice guidelines to improve digital literacy and online safety among women in semi-rural Pakistan..

Keywords: Digital Alienation; Uses And Gratifications Theory; Digital Literacy; Social Networking Sites; Privacy; Digital Divide.

Introduction

The twentieth-first century has been characterized by a deep communication pattern shift, led by the fast growth of the internet and digital media technologies. The internet currently connects billions of people all over the world, redefining human relationships, political engagement, and social relationships. Digital communication technologies have produced "cross-cultural encounters," allowing people to engage in virtual communities that cross geographical and cultural divides, as argued by Ess (2013).

In Pakistan, Social Media, as in the world, has developed as an intrinsic part of life which combines space for recreation, information, trade, and identification in one interactive world. Rather, however, it poses new sets of paradoxes. It is true that user-controlled social spaces provide access to empowerment through participation and self-determination, but they also produce new kinds of dependency and new forms of inequity. Researchers such as Bai et al. (2021) hold that the user, rather than acquiring greater control over technology, has become increasingly dominated by algorithmic patterns for controlling visibility, attention and activity called by them digital alienation. This is more evident amongst marginalised communities, such as women from semi rural areas having interlinked access difficulties from literacy, social infrastructure and cultural difficulties.

Digital Native

The idea that individuals are being "digital natives" is based on the theory that advances in technology are changing how individuals' brains function. Passively ingested information can lead to misconceptions and damage neural networks associated with emotional and cognitive development. "Digital natives" would appear to be socially inept as their online behavior is so divergent from actual behavior offline (Leshkevich & Motozhanets 2019).

This generation prefers social media very strongly and has shown a strong inclination towards community-building tools like Facebook, Instagram, TikTok and Snapchat, through which users can post videos. The user has lots of scope to be creative with these applications. It is also stated that the use of these applications has harmed their way of thinking and led them to become distant towards other people and organizations (Moharam and Mukherji, 2023).

With the fact that people have prefabricated sources of information at their disposal in this digital era, most of the time individuals simply imitate introspection. Material online does not, nonetheless, translate to wisdom. Additionally, being tech-savvy has the contrary outcome when a person's intellectual capital is not matched with their stuff on the web. A digital media consumer turns into a pseudo-intellectual because of the "adapted wisdom" at the end, which depends on quick searches over the internet from any device without thinking about the content being retrieved. Cognitive ability is, however, considered to be the fundamental trait of Homo sapiens. Those that can identify patterns, basic traits, and set long-term goals accomplish this through creative thinking. Reciprocal comprehension arises from creativity in interpersonal interaction (Hassan, 2020). Our encounters with technological advances are in essence contradictory. As much as they bring humanity an array of prospects to augment the quality of our lives, they never manage to live up to this promise, leaving us to contend with very difficult situations on an individual, national, organizational, and global level. Limited end user knowledge lead to a negative disruption to one's business and personal life; initiate serious financial issues. (Healy, 2021).

Technological innovation allows humans to individualize, represent oneself, and consequently, the virtual facility attracts the responsible with the idea that we can create and project distinctness through digital media.

Individualization has been infused into technological advances. The course of personal individuation is intertwined with pastoral modes of power; to say one does not want to express one's difference through electronic means would be as odd in the age of electronics as it would have been in the era of industry (Katarina, 2016)..

The Gendered Digital Divide in Pakistan

In Pakistan, digital inclusion is still unevenly distributed. Urban and male groups have greater connectivity and exposure to information and communication technologies (ICTs), while women particularly from rural and semi-urban regions still experience socio-cultural and economic obstacles.

The Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (PTA) identifies an ongoing "gender digital divide" where women's exposure to mobile phones and the internet is considerably lower than that of men. Due to things like economic restrictions, ingrained patriarchal views, and privacy concerns, women are not allowed in internet venues. As a result, their use of social networking sites (SNS) is either functional, inactive, or strictly controlled. The ladies of Layyah, a small area in South Punjab, are examined in this study as a significant illustration of how location, gender, and technology interact. It will look at how women from the so-called "digital native" generation—those who were born into the internet era—are adjusting to social media platforms in this environment of cultural struggle and constraints.

The Paradox of Digital Modernity

In addition to promoting self-promotion, entrepreneurship, and innovation, social media sites like Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and Snapchat also reinforce categories of society and moral monitoring. Users may experience psychological weariness, privacy concerns, or internal reflection as a result of online surveillance and inspection environments. Digital alienation results from commercial surveillance's objectification and manipulation of the online self, according to Dainow (2016).

Women feel even more alienated in traditional societies because of the tension between using the internet and cultural expectations of restraint and modesty. According to Comor (2010), when surfing goes against local value systems, even

active users may become alienated. Therefore, digital alienation encompasses mental, physical, and cultural disengagement from online involvement and cannot be limited to a lack of access.

Involvement in digital existence is now regarded as a condition for complete social and economic integration in modern society. New communication technologies have rendered digital connectivity desirable, if not, in many respects, indispensable. The initial techno-utopian accounts predicted that the internet would break down established hierarchies and melt national and cultural borders, creating a so-called "flattened world." Despite this, the reluctance of inequality, gendered limitations, and differential access to technology undermines these deterministic prognoses.

In Pakistan, the media environment has been deeply disrupted from state-controlled broadcast to open digital spaces. These spaces, however, continue to be unevenly accessible.

In patriarchal and resource-scarce contexts, like Layyah in South Punjab, women's use of social media continues to be circumscribed, mediated by digital divides, cultural expectations, and privacy fears. Having an understanding of digital alienation in this sociocultural setting is thus critical in order to determine how women encounter empowering and constraining digital spaces. This research explores the everyday lives of women in Layyah as "digital natives" navigating connectivity and constraint..

Research Objectives

The research goals were streamlined to promote conceptual precision and create clear theoretical connections with the uses and gratifications theory (UGT). These goals resonate with the study's emphasis on ascertaining how women in Layyah found their place in a semi-rural, gendered digital space interact with social networking sites (SNS) and feel digital alienation.

To measure the certain gratifications (social, cognitive, affective, and entertainment) that women in Layyah aim to acquire from social networking sites (SNS) and how these gratifications differ in terms of social roles (housewives, students, professionals).

To examine how different levels of digital literacy, access, and socioeconomic status (digital capital) affect women's capability to acquire sought gratifications and how these dimensions contribute to experiences of digital alienation.

To investigate the ways in which privacy issues, social surveillance, and gendered cultural norms influence women's online self-presentation and involvement, mediating the association between media consumption and perceived empowerment.

To conceptualize the interplay among individual motivations (UGT) and structural barriers (digital divide, cultural policing, and gender norms) to explain why SNS use does not necessarily result in empowerment or belonging for women in semi-rural Pakistan.

Research Questions

In order to operationalize the objectives, the research responds to the following research questions (RQs):

RQ1. What are women in Layyah's social, cognitive, affective, and entertainment gratifications that they seek through their use of social networking sites (SNS)?

RQ2. How do digital literacy, technological access, and socioeconomic background variations influence women's capacity to achieve these gratifications and women's digital experience overall?

RQ3. How are privacy issues, familial surveillance, and cultural expectations

affecting women's online engagement, self-presentation, and sense of empowerment?

RQ4. How does the dialectics between individual drives (as UGT theorized them) and structural obstacles (digital divide, gender norms, and social control) shape experiences of digital disaffection?

RQ5. In what ways can the intersection of UGT with the notion of digital alienation give a richer perspective regarding women's negotiated digital agency in semi-rural contexts in Pakistan?

Literature Review

The phenomenon of digital alienation has been investigated through various dimensions technological, psychological, and cultural. Past literature identifies a range of intersecting factors that affect users' interactions with digital platforms, especially women in developing contexts. Grounded on previous literature and conceptual synthesis, five broad thematic areas guide this investigation: technological literacy and awareness, privacy and risk perception, efficacy beliefs and cultural norms, digital divide and trust, and behavioral intention and alienation effects.

Technological Awareness and Literacy

Technological literacy is key to comprehending the ways in which users interact with social media sites. It is used to describe the capability of users to access, assess, and appropriately use digital tools. Digital inclusion studies in South Asia (Ahmad & Tariq, 2023; Hassan, 2020) repeatedly indicate that limited functional awareness hinders full participation, particularly among women.

Semi-rural contexts are the place where users tend to have no training or exposure to productive and professional uses of SNS and thus depend upon informal learning or others' help. This limited digital potential aids in the passive consumption of media, with users scrolling, looking at, and sharing media but not often creating and profiting from it. People that use technology out of habit rather than because they truly understand what they're doing are said to have "digital dependency" in literature. Therefore, digital integration turns out to be rather superficial. While people are entertained, they are not truly empowered. In a country like Pakistan, where gender plays a significant role in day-to-day life, this lack of digital literacy only highlights more significant problems like unequal access to education, cultural hurdles, and a lack of basic amenities. In the end, rather than expressing digital alienation, technological training fuels it (Agha, 2024).

Privacy and Risk Perception

Privacy is a major barrier for women who want to participate online. According to research, women's worries about harassment, misinformation, or misuse of their information affect how they behave online in cultures where masculinity is pervasive (Agha, 2024). Consequently, many women limit themselves or remain concealed, often by taking on fictitious identities or keeping a low profile.

Scholars have called this "self-regulated invisibility" (Dainow, 2016). Essentially, women are always choosing how much to reveal and when to retreat. In Pakistan, things are far more challenging. All of this is heightened by ideas of humility and family honor. Because they care about other people's perceptions, women who are tech-savvy often keep to themselves. As a result, privacy issues are not just a technology issue; they are also intertwined with social standards. Ultimately, women's perceptions of the dangers of online life impact their sense of security, their sense of control, and whether or not they want to participate.

Efficacy Beliefs and Cultural Norms

Self-efficacy, or the belief that one can manage digital tasks, is a key component of people's online confidence. According to more recent research, these ideas are not only personal, building on Bandura's (1997) work. They are absorbed from society and our families and come from the world around us. Women find it difficult to distinguish between what their culture, family, and community expect of them and what they believe they are capable of (Healy, 2021).

Strict societal norms frequently prevent women in South Asia from employing their skills, even if they are proficient in technology or content creation. Her prospects are limited by her parents, patriarchal acceptance, and fear of being judged. She may therefore be aware of how to take part but feel as though she is not truly permitted. You can't always see that she has the talent but lacks the approval, so it's a form of exclusion.

Beliefs about your abilities so serve as the link, or barrier, between being tech-savvy and really participating. Women tend to retreat or remain silent when they feel powerless, which only serves to perpetuate the cycle of invisibility.

Digital Divide, Access, and Trust

Having a device or being online is only one aspect of the digital divide. It also raises the question of whether or not people actually trust technologies that are digital. As Healy and Hassan have pointed out, providing access does not ensure that people would use it. When online resources don't work properly together or the framework is fragile, people start becoming concerned about things like their data being abused. This is particularly detrimental to rural areas in Pakistan. People out there confront even greater obstacles because of the limited funding and erratic network.

Reliance on male homeowners for gadgets or internet accounts further restricts access for women. According to research on digital trust, ongoing engagement is reliant on both technical infrastructure and perceptions of reliability and security in online interactions. Users feel uncomfortable and alienated when there is a lack of trust, and they perceive digital platforms as weird or dangerous. Because disparities in material resources, institutional trust, and social capital all influence participation patterns, the digital gap in semi-rural areas is therefore multifaceted.

Behavioral Intention and Alienation Effects

Behavioral intention is the motivational orientation of users towards sustained use of digital media. Although UGT postulates that users look for media in terms of gratification and satisfaction, digital alienation studies complicate the postulation by revealing that excessive exposure results in emotional exhaustion, envy, and social withdrawal (Bai & Gao, 2021; Rui & Stefanone, 2016).

In Pakistan, new evidence is coming to light that social comparison, misinformation, and online moral policing lead to negative affective consequences, particularly for women. If social media is used as a ground for judgment instead of empowerment, behavioral intentions are redirected towards participation to avoidance. This results in decreased online exposure, disengagement, and eventually alienation a psychological state characterized by disconnection, loss of control, and reduced sense of belonging.

The paradox of digital modernity is highlighted by these alienation effects: the same technology designed to unite people may simultaneously encourage social disintegration, loneliness, and anxiety.

Theoretical Framework

Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT)

The Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) forms the analytical basis of this study. First developed by Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch (1973), UGT views audiences as active consumers who choose media to fulfill cognitive, affective, and social needs. For social networking sites, users search for gratifications like entertainment, belongingness, identity formation, and self-presentation (Whiting & Williams, 2013; Rui & Stefanone, 2016).

Yet, in unequal and gendered societies, the assumption of user autonomy is challenged. Structural barriers patriarchal norms, digital literacy disparities, and cultural surveillance limit women's capacity to function as fully autonomous agents. As such, their gratifications are incomplete or conflicted and induce psychological dissonance and alienation.

Linking UGT with Digital Alienation

The combining of UGT with the idea of digital alienation crosses micro-level user intentions with macro-level societal constraints. UGT describes why people use media, while digital alienation describes how those uses are restricted, deformed, or commercialized by outside systems. Combined, these paradigms enable an interactionist model of media use one that locates personal action within the parameters of structural and cultural power.

Social media refers to a collection of online applications such as Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram and other social networking platforms which establish ideological bases and technical foundation to produce and share the content generated by the users (Whitting and William, 2013).

Social networking sites is a tool for communication that facilitates consumers interact with billions of individuals on a global scale (Williams et al., 2012).

The theoretical concept behind the uses and gratifications approach is that individuals will opt for media in place of adversaries when it suits their purposes and delivers the potential gratification (Lariscy et al., 2011).

Uses and gratification theory offers a functional strategy towards mass media functions and its implication. One of the basic principles of uses and gratification theory is that audience members are aware of what they need, and how these needs dictate media decisions so that the needs can be met (Rui & Stefanone, 2016). How media use functions is this: "(1) psychological and social roots of wants; (2) anticipations of the media or other sources; (3) media or other sources; (4) media usage habits (5) the trends in media exposure; (6) satisfactions of demands; and (7) other implications, perhaps unintended" (Katz et al., 1973). For women in Layyah, gratification-seeking behavior (in terms of connection, entertainment, or learning) is always negotiated through lenses of gender norms, privacy anxiety, and differential access. The outcome is an evolving process of negotiated agency: women engage selectively, frequently switching between curiosity and caution, connection and withdrawal.

This theoretical integration allows further understanding of the way digital alienation presents not as absolute exclusion but as conditional participation influenced by technological, cultural, and psychological factors.

Research Methodology

Research Design

This qualitative study looks closely at how women in Layyah utilize social networking sites and how it affects and sometimes disrupts their lives. By focusing on these women's real-life experiences, feelings, and particular situations, the study investigates what it really means for them to navigate digital worlds. Instead, then forcing the women's experiences into predefined frames, the technique allows them to freely express how they perceive and use these platforms. The study, which is grounded in the uses and gratifications theory (UGT), asks women not just what they do online but also what they hope to get out of such interactions and how their local culture and personal beliefs impact genuinely beneficial outcomes.

Table: 4.1. Thematic Framework (Based on Study Variables)

Variable	Methodological Focus	Key Themes
Awareness / Technological Literacy	Understanding and use of SNS	Limited functional awareness; reliance on others; passive consumption
Risk Perception / Privacy Concerns	Privacy and safety management	Fear of exposure; family restrictions; anonymity
Efficacy Belief / Cultural Norms	Perceived control and empowerment	Gender norms; self-censorship; lack of training
Trust and Access (Digital Divide)	Inequality and participation gaps	Limited connectivity; economic barriers; low digital trust
Behavioral Intention / Alienation Effects	Psychological and social outcomes	Disconnection; low participation; comparison anxiety

Sampling and Participants

To give a realistic picture of what's going on, the study employed purposive sampling, hand-picking women who are engaged online and serve a variety of social roles in Layyah's semi-rural setting. Three groups of fifteen people each are present:

Educated Housewives: These are women who take care of their homes and use social media to unwind or stay in touch.

College Students: Social networking sites (SNS) are used by young, tech-savvy women for socializing, knowledge, and expressing oneself.

Professional Workers: Educators, medical professionals, or administrators who use social networking sites to communicate and obtain information. This allows the study to capture a variety of viewpoints, including age, education, and occupation, all of which influence how these women interact with and occasionally feel excluded from the digital world.

Table: 4.2. Partitipant of In-depth Interviews

Pseudonym	Group	Age	Notes
H1	Housewife	34	Basic smartphone, limited digital skills
H2	Housewife	29	Uses WhatsApp primarily
H3	Housewife	40	Sells textiles locally, uses FB marketplace via son
H4	Housewife	26	Learnt basic reels from neighbor
H5	Housewife	38	Privacy concerned; uses SNS for family updates
S1	Student	20	Active on TikTok; restricted by parents
S2	Student	22	Uses IG for study groups
S3	Student	19	Aspiring voice artist; limited platform knowledge
S4	Student	21	Employs SNS for entertainment
S5	Student	23	Occasional content creator
P1	Professional	30	Radio presenter; limited personal SNS
P2	Professional	35	School teacher; cautious online
P3	Professional	28	NGO worker; uses FB for awareness
P4	Professional	33	Small-business owner; uses FB marketplace
P5	Professional	27	Journalist; uses SNS professionally, but avoids personal exposure

Data Collection

In-depth, semi-structured interviews in Urdu provided the data, which was subsequently translated into English for analysis. Depending on what was most convenient for the participants, each interview was conducted online or in-person and lasted between 45 to 60 minutes. Open-ended questions in the interviews asked women to discuss topics such as:

Why they use social media and what they want to gain from it.

How they use it and what advantages they perceive.

Their experiences using the internet and being digitally literate

Concerns about their appearance, privacy, or feeling watched.

When they've felt worn out, alienated, or uncomfortable using the internet

Women were given the opportunity to tell their own tales within this framework, which also helped to keep the discussions on the topic of the study

Data Analysis

Every interview was transcribed word-for-word and examined through thematic analysis, using Braun and Clarke's six-step method:

Getting familiar with the data

Creating initial codes

Finding patterns and themes

Reviewing those themes

Defining and naming each theme

Writing it all up

The data was repeatedly examined for context and depth, and all coding was done by hand. Technological literacy, privacy and danger, cultural norms and perceptions

about digital aptitude, digital divisions and trust, and the consequences of utilizing (or not using) these platforms were the main topics that emerged from the literature. More crucial than simply collecting anecdotes was comprehending how women's digital experiences link to broader social and cultural factors, especially via the lenses of UGT and digital alienation.

Ethical Considerations and Trustworthiness

This study adhered to all relevant ethical guidelines set forth by the organization. All participants gave their informed consent, and their identities were hidden using pseudonyms. When conducting the interviews, local cultural norms were taken into account, especially those related to privacy and internet use. The following factors were taken into consideration in order to guarantee the validity of the findings.

Credibility: The researcher spent a lot of time with individuals and verified the accuracy of their answers.

Transferability: Others can apply these findings to many contexts thanks to the thorough, contextualized narratives.

Reliability: To guarantee consistency, thematic analysis was conducted twice and recorded.

Confirmability: To control for personal bias, the researcher maintained a reflective notebook.

Findings

From analyzing the 15 interviews, five main themes came up each tied to the key ideas driving the study:

Conditional Gratifications and Limited Awareness

Privacy, Risk, and Social Surveillance

Efficacy Beliefs and Cultural Control

Digital Capital, Trust, and Access Inequalities

Behavioral Intention and Alienation Effects

Each theme is illustrated below with real stories from participants and thoughtful interpretation.

Conditional Gratifications and Limited Awareness

People spent a lot of time on Facebook, WhatsApp, TikTok, and Instagram, mostly just scrolling, watching, and not really posting much themselves. Several participants noted limited awareness of utilizing these sites for economic, educational, or civic needs.

A college student noted: "I record and upload short videos, but I don't dare put my face up because my family will embarrass me." Another housewife reported: "I use Facebook to check what other people are doing; I don't know how people make money from it." These assertions show that although women gain affective gratifications (pleasure, belonging, distraction), they rarely gain instrumental gratifications (income, visibility, learning). This is in line with the subject of minimal functional awareness participants often become reliant on others for technical assistance and are passive consumers and not content producers.

UGT's assumption of active media agency is partly verified: women are motivated but

suffer bounded agency restricted by scarce literacy and contextual awareness. Gratifications are therefore conditional attained within restrictive behavioural boundaries that minimize transformative potential.

Privacy, Risk, and Social Surveillance

For women, worries about privacy and being watched by family or just the public shaped everything they did online. They talked about feeling like someone was always looking over their shoulder, so they held back. . Some made sure that only a small number could see anything, some posted hardly at all, and some concealed their true identity. According to one woman, "I sell cloth but I don't post my photo; my brother says it's dishonorable." The similar fear was expressed by a professional: "I speak freely on radio, but I keep a small profile online because trolls find you." Another clarified: "On Instagram, I go by a pseudonym." Girls displaying their faces online are frowned upon by my family. All of these tales demonstrate how women are prevented from occupying online space by fear, including fear of damaging their reputations and concern of violating gender norms. It transforms digital life into a continuous balancing act with customs and familial expectations, and it's not just about privacy.

This free, neutral space isn't the internet. It is influenced by culture, which establishes the guidelines for who is visible and who is not. As a gatekeeper, privacy concern makes women less visible until they become what Dainow (2016) referred to as "digital blindness." Even the concept of looking for love or a connection online is reframed as being more about avoiding controversy, remaining silent, and avoiding criticism than it is about having fun.

Efficacy Beliefs and Cultural Control

Being confident is more than just understanding how to do things online. This includes creating material, participating in discussions, and exchanging ideas. It is linked to the opinions of those around you and whether your family finds it acceptable. Without support from their families, even women who are proficient with technological devices are held back. one youngster stated bluntly, "My parents won't let me even if I know how to generate content," another said, "I intended to start a YouTube channel on academic subjects, but my husband told me that people will talk." A different lady stated: "My son helps me with navigating WhatsApp; I do not have the courage to do so by myself." So, women's sense of control isn't really about their skills it's about what's allowed, what's proper, what's expected.

Being torn between their abilities and their expectations, even the most capable women learn to limit themselves. Healy (2021) was accurate; Whether or not your community allows you to claim authority online is more important than skill alone. These ladies believe that digital freedom is something that must be negotiated. You never feel as though it is truly yours.

Digital Capital, Trust, and Access Inequalities

The playing field is uneven despite the fact that practically everyone owns a smartphone. Some women have trouble with unstable technology, poor connectivity, or simply being hesitant to use new apps. Concerns about money exacerbate the situation, and many women require family support, particularly when anything goes wrong. One mother stated, "Our net doesn't work properly; occasionally I ask my children to assist me when the telephone hangs," another expressed, "Even if I try to advocate for some explanation, people brand it as rumor," Women are not taken

seriously on the internet. So, owning a phone isn't enough. Without trust, reliable tech, or social backing, women stay on the edge of digital life present, but rarely seen or heard.

Behavioral Intention and Alienation Effects

Participants did recognize the value of SNS in entertainment and connection, but many reported emotional exhaustions, anxiety of comparison, and disillusionment. A student commented: "These apps waste time and make people jealous of each other." A professional contributed: "Sometimes I feel lonelier after scrolling. Everyone looks happy, and I feel my life is dull." Another housewife (H5) commented: "I like TikTok, but it also makes me feel that I am wasting my day. It's like addiction." These reflections show that gratifications notwithstanding, SNS use generates psychological alienation users are connected and yet feel apart, empowered but emotionally drained. UGT accounts for why people use (for gratification), but not how excessive exposure can create alienation. The experiences of participants unveil a paradox of digital modernity: the very sites of connection also amplify insecurity and comparison with others. Alienation is not the result of exclusion but of being overconnected with unmet needs.

Synthesis of Findings

Together, the five themes depict that women's use of SNS in Layyah captures a dynamic of negotiated agency alive and restricted, literate and reliant, connected and disconnected.

Depth of participation is shaped by awareness,

Perceived risk moderates observability,

Efficacy beliefs control confidence,

Trust and access rule inclusion, and

Behavioral intention encapsulates the psychological consequences of online participation.

The outcomes push Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) further by showing gratifications to be socially mediated and structurally constrained rather than being freely sought. Women's agency is present in what might be termed conditional empowerment the capability of participating digitally but under constant constraints of morality, literacy, and infrastructure.

Finally, digital alienation here is not lack of use but use under constraint a condition under which women experience digital life both as participants and outsiders.

Analysis

Data analysis was informed by the five research questions that emanated from the study's objectives and theory. The questions are discussed below with regard to thematic patterns, conceptual associations, and theoretical implications under the theorizing of Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) and digital alienation.

RQ1: What kinds of social, cognitive, affective, and entertainment gratifications do women in Layyah pursue through their usage of social networking sites (SNS)?

The analysis shows that women use SNS mainly for affective and entertainment gratifications, such as emotional relief, social connectedness, and escapism from day-to-day home life. These uses are consistent with UGT's fundamental assumption that

audiences purposefully select media to fulfill psychological and social needs. Nevertheless, the data unveil that women's use is mostly non-instrumental based on leisure and not learning, civic engagement, or economic possibility.

The limited gratification diversity implies that although Layyah women are motivated consumers, their capacity to achieve transformative benefits from SNS is limited by surrounding conditions like low levels of digital literacy and constraining cultural expectations. Gratifications are therefore conditional and surface-level, offering emotional comfort but hardly leading to personal or collective empowerment.

RQ2: In what ways do digital literacy, access to technology, and socioeconomic status influence women's capacity to acquire these gratifications and, more broadly, their digital lives?

Analysis illustrates that digital literacy and digital capital are determining factors in the manner in which users attain preferable gratifications. Women who are more educated or professionally exposed are more competent and assured in operating in online environments, whereas women who are poorly educated or short of resources have to rely on family members for support.

Socioeconomic disparities also affect access quality fluctuating internet connectivity, shared computers, and minimal exposure to digital tools limit sustained interaction. The disparities generate differentiated use experiences: digitally literate women enjoy selective empowerment, while less literate users become passive actors in the digital landscape.

Theoretically, the discovery expands UGT to show that merely motivated use cannot guarantee satisfaction. Digital capital, a structural variable that dictates how human agency works in unequal technological and social settings, mediates access to gratifications.

RQ3: How do privacy issues, family monitoring, and cultural norms impact women's online engagement, self-presentation, and feelings of empowerment?

Privacy issues and social monitoring appeared to be key determinants mediating women's web presence. Avoidance of reputation loss, disapproval by family, and criticism from community confine women's exposure and self-presentation. Thus, online activity is no candid deployment of agency but a calculated performance of respectability.

UGT suggests that users look for gratifications like self-presentation, belonging, and identity construction through media usage. In this research, these gratifications are bounded by patriarchal standards linking female visibility with impropriety. Online behavior by women demonstrates a dual consciousness of wanting digital participation yet being tempered and censored.

Therefore, SNS empowerment is still symbolic, not substantive. The online setting mimics offline hierarchies, as shown here, and demonstrates that the ability to pursue gratifications is socially conditioned, not freely exercised.

RQ4: How does the interplay between individual motivations (as characterized by UGT) and structural obstacles (digital divide, gender norms, and social control) lead to experiences of digital alienation?

You begin to understand the true meaning of digital alienation for women when you examine the conflict between agency and structural limitations. They want to communicate and express themselves on social media, but they encounter several obstacles, such as inadequate infrastructure, strict gender norms, and ongoing surveillance. Therefore, while they do act with intention, their actual capabilities are limited. Although they have strict boundaries, their agency is real. People have the choice to utilize media whatever they choose, based on their own motives, according to the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT). But in this case, that isn't really true.

The study demonstrates that social hierarchies and uneven access affect freedom, which is never absolute. Though their participation is fragmented and conditional, women are not excluded from digital places. Not because they are unable to participate, but rather because their experience is fragmented, continually disputed, and, to be honest, very draining, they ultimately feel alienated. Therefore, complete exclusion is not the same as digital alienation. It concerns the discrepancy between women's desires and their real capabilities. They join social media in search of empowerment, but they keep running across the same obstacles, so even when they do participate, it frequently devolves into a combination of reliance and annoyance.

RQ5: How can an intersection of UGT with the concept of digital alienation yield a more holistic explanation of women negotiated digital agency in semi-rural settings of Pakistan?

Comparing digital alienation with UGT helps us understand what's actually going on. As UGT anticipates, women in Layyah utilize social media to keep connected and for emotional reasons. However, the truth is that they also have to cope with societal pressure, shoddy infrastructure, and the psychological effects of being watched or evaluated all the time. The digital realm lacks democracy and is rife with restrictions that drain you. The statement "they have access, so they are empowered" is not accurate. Negotiating between what you want to do and what you're permitted to do is the key to true empowerment on the internet.

Although women do have some agency, it is always limited. They gain something from it, but they also experience worry from comparing themselves to others, digital tiredness, and the constant fear of being watched for their behavior. This concept demonstrates how context is always connected to true empowerment on the internet. Women must strive for it within, not outside of, the confines of inequality and patriarchy. Women are connected and expressive, but they are also constrained and may feel cut off from their own digital lives. This phenomenon is better described as "conditional empowerment."

Conclusion

Social media is used for connecting, sharing, and communication these days. For women in Layyah, social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, TikTok, and YouTube offer both opportunities and challenges. These websites give women the opportunity to interact with others and entertain themselves, but they also reinforce past injustices, which lessens the extent to which women actually feel like they belong and have agency online.

The study found that women mostly use the internet to get emotional support, a change of pace, or companionship. But that rarely leads to real empowerment or a way out of their social situation. Why? Because they are still hampered by things like deeply rooted gender norms, privacy issues, and a lack of computer literacy. The result

is "conditional empowerment" since women continue to use the internet, but only in ways that are socially acceptable, which only makes them feel more dependent on these online resources and alienated.

It is clear that women in these areas do not truly have the right to use media as they see fit when examined through the lens of UGT. Cultural conventions, their degree of digital proficiency, and whether they even have reliable access are some of the factors that affect their choices. Digital alienation adds another dimension, showing how all these structural and cultural barriers turn what ought to be unrestricted, voluntary participation into a limited and sometimes grating experience. What is the true meaning of this? It means we need laws that make women feel safer and more at ease online, as well as culturally appropriate digital literacy programs. Allowing women to log in is not as vital as ensuring they can utilise the internet on their own behalf with true autonomy, security, and skill.

Limitations and Future Scope

Similar to all qualitative research, the study has some limitations that guide future research. Employing the use of snowball sampling limited the generalizability of the outcomes in that the participants were sourced from certain social networks within Layyah. Although this method facilitated the in-depth examination of the lived experiences, it does not make a claim to statistical representativeness. Subsequent research using quantitative or mixed methodology may assess the larger patterns of digital competence, risk perception, and effectiveness among various populations and regions in Pakistan.

The current research was limited mainly to socio-cultural factors affecting digital alienation. The studies in the future can include political, economic, and institutional factors to provide a more comprehensive understanding of digital inclusion. Further, involving national or international experts from technology, media policy, or gender studies would increase comparative and theoretical richness.

Methodologically, an ethnographic or a longitudinal method would shed light on how digital practices among women change over time as technology, access, and the norms of society keep shifting. Such a study would also be able to uncover how differences between regions urban vs. rural, provincial vs. metropolitan influence empowerment and alienation patterns. Lastly, since digital technologies and social media sites continue to change so fast, the experience of digital alienation is also dynamic. Future research must continue to probe how new technologies (e.g., algorithmic AI, influencer economies, digital work) transform women's agency and representation on the internet. Even though the main sites of contact between incentive and constraint have been established in this work, more research can help us understand how digital involvement becomes equal, meaningful, and empowering in rapidly evolving societies.

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